

1 **MONITORING WINEMAKING PROCESS USING TYROSINE INFLUENCE IN THE**
2 **EXCITATION-EMISSION MATRICES OF WINE**

3
4 Mónica PALOMINO-VASCO*, María Isabel ACEDO-VALENZUELA, María Isabel RODRÍGUEZ-
5 CÁCERES, Nielene MORA-DÍEZ

6
7 Department of Analytical Chemistry and Research Institute on Water, Climate Change and
8 Sustainability (IACYS), Faculty of Sciences, University of Extremadura, Badajoz, 06006, Spain

9 * monicapv@unex.es

10
11
12 **Abstract:** Wine samples collected during the winemaking process have been analyzed employing a
13 previously optimized UHPLC-FD method, determining their biogenic amines and amino acids profile.
14 The results obtained have been submitted to a statistical analysis from which it was extracted that the
15 most influential analyte was tyrosine. Thanks to its fluorescence, a method for its determination by
16 excitation-emission matrices has been proposed. The accuracy of the method has been checked by
17 means of Elliptical Joint Confidence Region test. The winemaking process has been monitored with
18 this method, obtaining a faster and cheaper way to follow the process.

19
20 **Keywords:** tyrosine; wine; EEM; PARAFAC; chemometrics; **chromatography**

22 1. Introduction

23 Amino acids (AAs) are a subgroup within the organic acids that contribute to the organoleptic
24 and nutritional properties (R. M. Callejón, Troncoso, & Morales, 2010; Robles, Fabjanowicz, Chmiel,
25 & Płotka-Wasyłka, 2019). In particular, AAs generate volatile compounds related to aroma
26 (Petropoulos, Metafa, Kotseridis, Paraskevopoulos, & Kallithraka, 2018; Valdés et al., 2019).
27 Moreover, they can be used to control the evolution of acidification during winemaking (Robles et al.,
28 2019).

29 In wine, AAs can come directly from the raw material and are metabolized by yeasts, acting as
30 a source of nitrogen (Arrieta & Prats-Moya, 2012; R. M. Callejón et al., 2010; Valdés et al., 2019).
31 **However**, they can also appear as yeast waste after the fermentation or be generated due to enzymatic
32 degradation of proteins (R. M. Callejón et al., 2010). Its concentration and profile depend on several
33 factors (R. M. Callejón et al., 2010; Petropoulos et al., 2018; Valdés et al., 2019). Within them, tyrosine
34 is a non-essential AA that reaches the human body through the hydroxylation of phenylalanine or
35 through the intake of food containing it (PubChem, 2020; Schenck & Maeda, 2018). **It forms part of**
36 **many proteins, and is the precursor of some important neurotransmitters** (Fernstrom & Fernstrom,
37 2007; PubChem, 2020). It also participates in the synthesis of melanin, catecholamines and some
38 thyroid hormones (Slominski, Zmijewski, & Pawelek, 2012).

39 Apart from that, AAs are the precursors of biogenic amines (BAs), compounds with toxic
40 activity that can be harmful for the human health (He et al., 2016; Meléndez, Sarabia, & Ortiz, 2016;
41 Palomino-Vasco, Rodríguez-Cáceres, Mora-Diez, Pardo-Botello, & Acedo-Valenzuela, 2019;
42 Papageorgiou et al., 2018). The concentration of BAs in wine could vary between a few and 50 mg L⁻¹,
43 and although it is important to keep this concentration as low as possible, there are no laws regulating
44 their maximum concentration in wine. Its profile also depends on several factors (Papageorgiou et al.,
45 2018; Peña-Gallego, Hernández-Orte, Cacho, & Ferreira, 2012; Perestrelo, Bordiga, Locatelli, Silva, &
46 Câmara, 2020). Hence, the joint determination of AAs and BAs is interesting to both researchers and

47 industry, since they can be used as a quality or safety index, or as an ageing or authenticity indicator
48 (R. M. Callejón et al., 2010; He et al., 2016; Palomino-Vasco, Acedo-Valenzuela, Rodríguez-Cáceres,
49 & Mora-Diez, 2019; Robles et al., 2019).

50 AAs can be determined directly by UV, but their absorption is in a very non-specific area where
51 almost all compounds and solvents **absorb**. Only tyrosine, tryptophan and phenylalanine present
52 chromophore groups that allow them to be determined by fluorescence. The determination and
53 quantification of BAs in wine is also challenging due to the complexity of the matrix and the presence
54 of several BAs in the same sample, which **are** normally present low concentrations. **Moreover, BAs do**
55 **not present adequate characteristics for their determination by spectrophotometric techniques due to**
56 **their structure**. Therefore, AAs and BAs should normally be pre-concentrated and/or derivatised or
57 determined by MS. The most commonly used methods for their determination are separative techniques
58 (R. M. Callejón et al., 2010; Ferré, González-Ruiz, Guillarme, & Rudaz, 2019; Önal, Tekkeli, & Önal,
59 2013; Palomino-Vasco, Acedo-Valenzuela, et al., 2019; Papageorgiou et al., 2018).

60 On another note, fluorescence spectroscopy is a non-invasive instrumental technique widely
61 used in food matrices since it allows to obtain information about molecular structure and functions, and
62 allows characterizing the foodstuffs. Other advantages are its sensitivity and selectivity, as well as
63 being a quick and easy technique to use (Airado-Rodríguez, Durán-Merás, Galeano-Díaz, & Wold,
64 2011; Azcarate, Teglia, Karp, Camiña, & Goicoechea, 2017; Raquel M. Callejón et al., 2012;
65 Carbonaro et al., 2019; Ríos-Reina et al., 2019). Within the different ways to employ fluorescence
66 spectroscopy, excitation-emission matrices (EEMs) are one of the best ways to obtain a lot of
67 information about the studied system, that can then be extracted using chemometrics. PARAFAC
68 (PARAllel FACtor analysis) is the most used second-order algorithm for matrix decomposition, and it
69 has been used in many food samples (Airado-Rodríguez et al., 2011; Azcarate et al., 2017; Raquel M.
70 Callejón et al., 2012).

71 Several authors have employed the AAs and/or BAs profile of wines obtained by separate
72 techniques in combination with chemometrics for wine differentiation or monitoring along time (R. M.
73 Callejón et al., 2010; Jiménez Moreno, Torrea Goñ, & Ancín Azpilicueta, 2003; Ordóñez, Callejón,
74 Troncoso, & García-Parrilla, 2017; Palomino-Vasco, Rodríguez-Cáceres, et al., 2019). However, we
75 have no evidence of studies that determine the AAs and BAs profile during young wines winemaking.
76 Therefore, this was the first objective of this research, employing a previously optimized
77 chromatographic method. The statistical study of the obtained concentrations would give us
78 information about the most influential analytes in the variance. Furthermore, and taking into account
79 that some analytes are fluorescent, the second objective was the obtention of the EEMs of wine
80 samples collected during winemaking. The application of chemometrics and the correlation between
81 the chromatographic and the fluorescent results would result in the proposal of a simpler and more
82 economical way of monitoring the winemaking which, to the best of our knowledge, has never been
83 proposed.

84

85 **2. Materials and Methods**

86 **2.1 Chemicals**

87 The analytes determined in this study were putrescine (PUT), histamine (HIM), tyramine
88 (TYM), glutamic acid (GLU), serine (SER), cadaverine (CAD), tryptamine (TRY), 2-phenylethylamine
89 (PEA), lysine (LYS), arginine (ARG) and phenylalanine (PHE), purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA);
90 agmatine (AGM), purchased from Alfa-Aesar (Germany); ethanolamine (ETA) and tyrosine (TYR),
91 purchased from Merck (Germany); histidine (HIS), purchased from Fluka (Spain); and glycine (GLY)
92 and tryptophan (TRP), purchased from Panreac (Spain). 1-octylamine (OCT; Fluka, Spain) was
93 employed as internal standard in the chromatographic method. A stock solution of 10000 mg L⁻¹ of
94 each AA and of 5000 mg L⁻¹ of each BA was prepared by solving the adequate amount of the

95 powder/liquid presentation in ultrapure water (Merck Millipore, USA). Solutions were stored at 4°C in
96 darkness, and were daily used to prepare the working analyte solutions.

97 For the derivatization reaction, a boric acid/sodium borate buffer (0.6 M; pH 10.50) was weekly
98 prepared by diluting the adequate amount of boric acid (Merck, Germany) in ultrapure water (Merck
99 Millipore, USA), and adjusting the pH with NaOH (Panreac, Spain). A solution of 0.4 mg of o-
100 phthalaldehyde (OPA; Sigma-Aldrich, USA) in 10.0 mL of MeOH (Panreac, Spain) was also weekly
101 prepared. Then, the derivatization reagent was prepared by mixing in a 5.0 mL volumetric flask 1.6 mL
102 of the OPA solution and 1.2 mL of 2-mercaptoethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). The flask was filled up
103 to the mark with the aforementioned boric acid/sodium borate buffer. Before its use, the derivatization
104 reagent was filtered (0.22 µm membrane nylon filters; Teknokroma, Spain).

105 Mobile phase employed for the chromatographic separation was composed with acetonitrile
106 UHPLC-grade (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), methanol UHPLC-grade (Panreac, Spain) and a TRIS buffer,
107 which was prepared by the dilution of the adequate amounts of Trizma® base (2-amino-2-
108 (hydroxymethyl)-1,3-propanediol; Sigma-Aldrich, USA) and tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane
109 hydrochloride (Acros, Spain) to obtain a concentration of 0.10 M and a pH of 8.30. Mobile phase was
110 filtered (0.22 µm membrane nylon filter; Teknokroma, Spain), and ultrasonicated before its use.

111 Synthetic wine employed was prepared by dissolving the adequate amount of L-(+)-tartaric acid
112 (Scharlau, Spain) to get a 3.0 g L⁻¹ concentration, in a 13% (v/v) EtOH (Panreac, Spain) aqueous
113 solution. pH was adjusted to 3.50 employing NaOH (Panreac, Spain).

114 Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVPP; Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was employed to remove the
115 polyphenols of the wine samples.

116

117 **2.2 Winemaking samples**

118 Wine samples were generously donated by the experimental winery of the University of
119 Extremadura during the winemaking process of a ‘Tempranillo’ grape young wine.

120 Samples were daily collected in the winery; and stored at -20°C and in dark until analysis.
121 Information about the winemaking process was given by the winemaker, who informed when the
122 different fermentations began according to the typical analyses of the winery (i.e. density control or
123 alcohol content).

124

125 ***2.3 Instrumentation and software***

126 For the chromatographic analysis of the samples, an Agilent Model 1260 Infinity High
127 Performance Liquid Chromatograph (Agilent Technologies Inc., USA) equipped with an online
128 degasser, quaternary pump (G1311B), column oven compartment (G1316A), autosampler (G1329B),
129 UV-VIS diode-array detector (G1315D) and fluorescence detector (G1321B) was employed.
130 ChemStation software was used for data treatment and instrument control. The analytical separation
131 was carried out in a Zorbax Eclipse XDB-C18 analytical column (100 x 4.6 mm; 1.8 µm; Agilent
132 Technologies Inc., USA).

133 For the obtention of the fluorescence EEMs, a Cary Eclipse Varian spectrofluorometer (Agilent
134 Technologies Inc., USA) connected by a GPIB488 card to a PC was employed. The instrument was
135 equipped with two Czerny-Turner monochromators, a constant xenon light source and a
136 photomultiplier tube as detector. Measurements were made in a 1.0 cm quartz cell. Cary Eclipse's own
137 software was used for equipment control and data acquisition.

138 Central composite experimental design was carried out employing The Unscrambler v9.7
139 (CAMO Software, Japan). Statistical analyses were performed using XLSTAT software (Addinsoft,
140 France). EEM_corr routine for MATLAB (Chiappini, Alcaraz, Goicoechea, & Olivieri, 2019) was
141 freely downloaded from <https://fcb.web1.unl.edu.ar/laboratorios/ladaq/download/>. Multivariate data
142 analyses were done employing MatLab R2016B (The MathWorks Inc., USA) and the MVC2 routine
143 (Olivieri, Wu, & Yu, 2009), available at www.iquir-conicet.gov.ar/descargas/mvc2.rar.

144

145 **2.4 Chromatographic determination**

146 The chromatographic determination of the analytes was carried out following an automatic
147 UHPLC-FLD method previously proposed by our investigation group (Palomino-Vasco, Acedo-
148 Valenzuela, et al., 2019). Briefly, it employed a fully automated derivatization reaction, making use of
149 an injection program that mixes the reagents sequentially before injecting them into the column.
150 Separation was performed at 50°C, with a flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹, and the fluorescent derivatives
151 were monitored at 356/445 nm. The peak area/internal standard area ratio was used as analytical signal.
152 Both the conditions of the automatic injection and the gradient used for the separation of the derivatives
153 are summarized in Tables in the aforementioned article. Also, all the information about the
154 establishment of the calibration curves as well as the analysis of real samples is extensively explained
155 in it.

156

157 **2.5 Fluorometric determination**

158 The fluorescence EEMs of the analytes were obtained by increasing the excitation wavelength
159 from 200 to 320 nm at 5 nm steps; and recording the emission spectra from 275 to 450 nm, every 1 nm.
160 Excitation and emission slits were both set at 5 nm, and photomultiplier voltage was set at 600 V. All
161 the measurements were made at room temperature.

162 For the establishment of the three-dimensional model, a central composite experimental design
163 was employed, with a total of 16 samples. Also, four validation samples were incorporated. Twenty-six
164 real wine samples were analysed.

165 Calibration and validation samples were prepared by the dissolution of the adequate aliquots of
166 the stock analyte solutions with synthetic wine to a final volume of 10.0 mL. For the obtention of the
167 EEMs of the real wine samples, a 10% (v/v) dilution in synthetic wine was employed. PVPP cleaning
168 was made after the dilution and prior to the analysis. For this procedure, 0.5 g of PVPP were added to
169 10.0 mL of the diluted sample in a Falcon tube; and sonicated for 5 min to homogenate. Then, the tubes

170 were centrifuged for 2 min at 3000 rpm, to separate the phases. Cleaned wine was transferred to the
171 quartz cell to its measurement.

172

173 **3. Results and discussion**

174 ***3.1 Chromatographic determination of the analytes during the winemaking process***

175 All the samples collected during the winemaking process were chromatographed and compared,
176 and **only those corresponding to the most significant changes or corresponding to important milestones**
177 **were analysed** (i.e. start of the alcoholic or malolactic fermentation). Thus, the analytes concentrations
178 of seven days of the process were obtained (Table 1). The samples were analysed employing the
179 methodology aforementioned (section 2.4). Because the presence of matrix effect, it was decided to
180 analyse the samples using the standard addition method in combination with the internal standard
181 method, employing the peak area/internal standard area ratio as analytical signal. **The quality**
182 **parameters of this methodology, as well as the recovery values in real samples that demonstrate that the**
183 **values obtained are accurate and real, can be found in the article where this method is optimised**
184 **(Palomino-Vasco, Acedo-Valenzuela, et al., 2019).**

185 As it can be seen in Table 1, most analytes undergo hardly any changes during the winemaking
186 process. The analytes that varied the most were TYR (whose concentration was the highest in general
187 and, moreover, increased with the passing of the days) and ARG (whose concentration in the must was
188 high, but decreased greatly after the start of alcoholic fermentation, remaining constant the rest of the
189 days). **Although studies found in the literature do not reach a clear consensus on the behaviour of the**
190 **evolution of each AA during winemaking, some authors have found similar results regarding the**
191 **increase in TYR concentration throughout the days of fermentation (Izquierdo Cañas, García Romero,**
192 **Gómez Alonso, Fernández González, & Palop Herreros, 2008; Lorenzo et al., 2017). These studies**
193 **propose that this increase may be caused by the presence of alcoholic fermentation lees, as well as by**
194 **yeast autolysis, which generates several protein degradation products, including AAs. Furthermore, it is**

195 also suggested that the prophylaxis of acid-lactic bacteria with carboxylase activity during malolactic
196 fermentation may influence the increase in TYR concentration. On the other hand, in the case of the
197 ARG, other authors do seem to agree, and several have reported a significant decrease in its
198 concentration along time (Izquierdo Cañas et al., 2008). Thus, the values obtained during this study
199 seem to be in accordance with those found in the literature.

200 It can also be noted that on 10th day (start of malolactic fermentation) there was a slight increase
201 in the concentration of TRP, as well as another slight increase on 25th day. However, in general, except
202 in the case of TYR and ARG, the initial and final concentrations of all analytes were very similar. On
203 the other hand, LYS was detected on all the samples, but in concentrations below the LOQ, and HIM,
204 TYM, TRY and PEA were not detected in any samples. This can be an indication of the good quality of
205 the wine, since the content of BAs is very low and, in addition, neither HIM or TYM, which are the
206 two most harmful BAs for the human beings, were present.

207

208 ***3.2 Statistical analysis of the chromatographic data***

209 Since there was no great variability in the data obtained except for TYR and ARG, it was
210 decided to study it statistically to check whether these were indeed the most influential analytes during
211 the winemaking process, which could simplify its monitorization.

212 Firstly, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was carried out. Covariance matrix was
213 employed because data was dimensionally homogenous and presented similar mean values. This type
214 of PCA assigns more weight to those variables with greater variance. For those concentrations found
215 below the LOD or LOQ, the missing value was replaced by the corresponding LOD/2 or LOQ/2.

216 It was obtained that two principal components explained 93.0% of the variance. The loadings
217 graph is showed in Figure 1A. PC1 explained 82.0% of variance, and was principally constituted by the
218 positive contribution of TYR (82.1%) and the negative contribution of ARG (16.4%). On the other
219 hand, PC2 explained 11.0% of variance, and was principally constituted by the positive contribution of

220 ARG (81.8%), TYR (16.4%) and TRP (1.4%). Taking this information into account, it can be said that
221 the analyte that have the most weight in the data variance and, therefore, have the greatest influence on
222 the winemaking process is TYR, followed far behind by ARG and TRP.

223 Figure 1B shows the scores graph obtained for the different samples. Considering the
224 information obtained by the winemaker when the samples were collected, some stages of the
225 winemaking process can be seen into the graph. Thus, the initial must (day 0) is the most different
226 sample (highest concentration of ARG); the 3rd day started the alcoholic fermentation (drastic reduction
227 of ARG concentration); the 10th day started the malolactic fermentation; and then, the samples post-
228 malolactic fermentation presented an increasing TYR concentration.

229 It can therefore be said that one way of monitoring the winemaking process would be to control
230 the concentration of TYR in the samples, as its concentration raised during the winemaking process,
231 and it is the most influential analyte **as shown in the statistical analysis, since it explains the 82.1%**
232 **variance within the Principal Component 1, which accounts for 82.0% of the explanation of the total**
233 **variance.**

234 In order to contrast the information obtained through PCA, it was decided to carry out a cluster
235 analysis, both non-hierarchical and hierarchical. In the case of the non-hierarchical analysis, the k-
236 means methodology was selected. Although it was not possible to separate the samples into different
237 groups, the class profile obtained made it clear that the most influential analyte was TYR (**Figure 1C**).
238 On the other hand, Ward's method was selected as the hierarchical methodology. In this case, three
239 different classes were obtained (**Figure 1D**). The first class included the initial samples (days 0 and 3),
240 which corresponded with the must and the alcoholic fermentation start. The second class consisted
241 exclusively of the 10th day, which corresponds to the start of malolactic fermentation. Finally, the last
242 class is made up of the remaining samples, which are those collected after the start of malolactic
243 fermentation. The class profile obtained with this method (**Figure 1E**) presented the same information
244 as the previous one, TYR being the most influential analyte. However, in this case, ARG presented

245 some importance in class 1 (where it was produced the drastic reduction of the ARG concentration),
246 and TRP was important in class 2 (the slight increase in its concentration that was aforementioned in
247 section 3.1).

248 **3.3 Fluorometric approach to the problem**

249 Bearing in mind the information obtained of the statistical analysis, and taking into account that
250 TYR presents fluorescence, a new approach to the monitoring of the winemaking process was
251 proposed. For that reason, the following experiences were made for determining the best conditions for
252 the fluorometric measurements.

253 Firstly, and employing conventional mode, EEMs of the fluorometric analytes were registered
254 between 250 and 500 nm (each 1 nm), exciting between 200 and 320 nm (each 5 nm), with a voltage of
255 600 V and the slits opened 5 nm. It was checked that TYR, TRP and PHE, and their respective biogenic
256 amines (TYM, TRY and PEA), were fluorescent (aqueous medium, no pH adjustment). The most
257 fluorescent analytes were TYR and TYM, followed by TRP and TRY. PHE and PEA presented a lot
258 lower fluorescence. It was also checked that each biogenic amine presented the same $\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em}$ as its
259 precursor amino acid, although each pair of analytes presented the maximum fluorescence at different
260 $\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em}$. So, TYM and TYR presented the maximum fluorescence at 276/356 nm; TRY and TRP
261 presented it at 274/301 nm; and PHE and PEA presented it at 257/280 nm. Taking into account that
262 TRY, TYM and PEA were not detected in any wine sample, and that the concentrations of PHE ranged
263 between 0.1 – 0.2 mg L⁻¹ and its low fluorescence, only TYR and TRP were finally selected as analytes
264 for the fluorometric method.

265 Synthetic wine was registered in these conditions to check that no fluorescence (except light
266 dispersion) was observed. No fluorescence of wine sample was observed due the internal filter effect.
267 The same was observed when front-face mode was used, and therefore, dilution of wine samples was
268 necessary to observe fluorescence.

269 Wine dilutions were made with MilliQ water and synthetic wine to search for differences, and it
270 was decided to use synthetic wine to help buffer the samples. Also, tests were made to find the best
271 dilution, trying to maintain the greater quantity of wine and obtaining the less internal filter, finally
272 choosing 10% dilution. After dilution, it was studied how the cleaning of the wine with PVPP affected,
273 and it was found that PVPP eliminated both polyphenols and part of the internal filter from the sample.

274 Finally, the instrumental conditions were adjusted and measurements were made in the range of
275 275 - 450 nm (every 1 nm), with the sample being excited every 5 nm between 200 and 320 nm. No
276 changes in voltage or slits opening were necessary.

277

278 ***3.4 Establishment of the fluorometric calibration and validation with the chromatographic data***

279 Once the conditions of the fluorometric measurements were optimized, a central composite
280 experimental design was proposed to establish the calibration data test. TRP concentrations ranged
281 between 0.16 – 1.00 mg L⁻¹, and TYR concentrations ranged between 0.19 – 2.00 mg L⁻¹ (taking into
282 account the concentrations found by the chromatographic method and the dilution of the samples).
283 Three more samples were added that presented only one analyte or any of them. Also, four validation
284 samples were prepared with analytes concentrations different from those employed in the calibration
285 data set. On the other hand, the wine samples analysed by UHPLC-FLD were also fluorometrically
286 measured and, taking as nominal concentrations the concentrations obtained by the chromatographic
287 method, acted as a second validation set.

288 After obtaining the EEMs, the *EEM_corr* routine (Chiappini et al., 2019) was used to eliminate
289 Rayleigh dispersion. PARAFAC was then applied to determine the number of components and to
290 predict the concentrations of the samples. Both the test samples and the previously analysed wine
291 samples were employed as validation files, obtaining that three components explained the system, by
292 both the CORCONDIA and the model fit criteria. For the determination of the number of components,
293 all modes were restricted to non-negative, since neither concentrations nor spectra can take negative

294 values. The three-dimensional spectra of the components obtained are represented in **Figure 2**. The first
295 one (C1) corresponds to TRP, while the third one (C3) corresponds to TYR. The second one (C2) must
296 be some unknown component in the wine.

297 Then, the concentrations of the validation samples were predicted and the results were
298 compared with the nominal values. **Also, eleven replicates with the analyte's concentration values of**
299 **one of the test samples were prepared and predicted, to obtain the values of repeatability. In the**
300 **optimized conditions, a relative standard deviation (RSD) of 0.87% and 0.75% was obtained for TYR**
301 **and TRP measurements, respectively.**

302 The prediction of the test samples was good for both analytes. However, in the wine validation
303 set, the prediction was only good for TYR values, which was checked employing the Elliptical Joint
304 Confidence Region test or EJCR (**Figure 3**) (Mandel & Linnig, 1957), taking into account the applied
305 dilution. Nominal values or chromatographic concentrations, as appropriate, as well as the percentage
306 recovery are shown in the Table 2. Predicted values for TRP in wine samples were outside the
307 calibration range and the predictions were not good, so no data is presented. **The reason why the**
308 **prediction of TRP in real samples is not good, although it is in test samples, may be that TRP has lower**
309 **fluorescence intensity than TYR. This fact, together with its low concentrations in the wine samples (as**
310 **can be seen in the values obtained by chromatography in Table 1), may have caused very low signals**
311 **for its correct quantification. Furthermore, the emission wavelength of TRP is inside the UV zone (i.e.:**
312 **301 nm), while TYR emission wavelength (i.e.: 356 nm) is closer to the visible zone, so its signal may**
313 **have been affected by more constituents of the wine matrix, which could have influenced the signal or**
314 **generated more internal filtering.**

315

316 ***3.5 Monitoring of the winemaking process by EEMs***

317 Although the prediction of TRP in real wine samples is not good, the monitoring of the
318 winemaking process could be carried out by quantifying TYR concentration, since it generated good

319 results in accordance with the chromatographically obtained values and, moreover, it is the most
320 influential analyte according to the statistical study, as previously mentioned (section 3.2).

321 It was therefore decided to measure fluorometrically all the samples collected during the
322 winemaking process. The results are showed in Figure 4. The concentration of TYR undergoes a
323 progressive increase from the initial must until approximately the start of malolactic fermentation (day
324 10th), almost doubled at this point. In the following days, TYR concentration varied between 5.21 -
325 7.68 mg L⁻¹, presenting ups and downs with respect to the value assumed by the polynomial of grade
326 three which approximately explains its behaviour (red line in Figure 4). These variations can be
327 explained by two reasons. First, wine is a live system, in which the yeasts themselves are responsible
328 for homogenizing the sample inside the vat, since during the malolactic fermentation the winery staff
329 do not touch the wine. For this reason, the sample is not completely homogenized, and there may be
330 more variations than expected. Secondly, it must be taken into account that there are two opposite
331 processes that take place at the same time and that affect the concentration of TYR: on the one hand,
332 the yeasts consume TYR and part of it is transformed into TYM; on the other hand, the proteolysis and
333 autolysis of the yeasts results in more TYR.

334 Regarding the slight increase of TYR concentration in the last day, other authors (Lorenzo et
335 al., 2017) have studied how different parameters of winemaking (i.e.: temperature and alcoholic
336 degree) affect the concentrations of different AAs and BAs. In all the conditions they tested, the TYR
337 concentration after the malolactic fermentation was higher than that found after the alcoholic
338 fermentation, and they concluded that the final concentrations of the analytes depended on these
339 conditions. In our case, the rebound is not as pronounced, but the differences in the type of grapes,
340 temperature, alcoholic degree, yeast strains, etc. must be taken into account. In any case, this rebound
341 on the last day could be used as an indicator that fermentation is over and it is time to transfer the wine
342 to the bottles.

343

344 **4. Conclusions**

345 The determination and quantification of amino acids and biogenic amines in wine samples
346 collected during the winemaking process have been carried out by UHPLC-FLD. Then, a statistical
347 analysis of the data was carried out (PCA and Cluster Analysis), from which it was concluded that the
348 most influential analyte of data variance was TYR.

349 Thanks to the fluorescence of TYR, a method has been developed for its determination and
350 quantification by means of EEMs. An attempt has been made to determine TRP (a less influential but
351 also fluorescent analyte) together, but the quantification did not obtain good results. However, the
352 results for TYR concentration have been validated with the chromatographic methodology by means of
353 the ellipse test. The monitoring of TYR concentration throughout the winemaking process allowed to
354 determine the start and the end of malolactic fermentation. Therefore, EEMs could be used as a much
355 faster and cheaper method for monitoring the winemaking process through TYR concentration
356 monitoring.

357

358 **Acknowledgements**

359 This work was supported by to the Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad of Spain (Project
360 CTQ2017-82496-P) and the Junta de Extremadura (GR18041-Research Group FQM003 and project
361 IB16058), both co-financed by the European Funds for Regional Development. M. Palomino-Vasco is
362 grateful to the Junta de Extremadura for a FPI grant (PD16033).

363

364

365 **References**

- 366 Airado-Rodríguez, D., Durán-Merás, I., Galeano-Díaz, T., & Wold, J. P. (2011). Front-face
367 fluorescence spectroscopy: A new tool for control in the wine industry. *Journal of Food*
368 *Composition and Analysis*, 24(2), 257–264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2010.10.005>
- 369 Arrieta, M. P., & Prats-Moya, M. S. (2012). Free amino acids and biogenic amines in Alicante
370 Monastrell wines. *Food Chemistry*, 135(3), 1511–1519.
371 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2012.06.008>
- 372 Azcarate, S. M., Teglia, C. M., Karp, F., Camiña, J. M., & Goicoechea, H. C. (2017). A novel fast
373 quality control strategy for monitoring spoilage on mayonnaise based on modeling second-order
374 front-face fluorescence spectroscopy data. *Microchemical Journal*, 133, 182–187.
375 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2017.03.036>
- 376 Callejón, R. M., Troncoso, A. M., & Morales, M. L. (2010). Determination of amino acids in grape-
377 derived products: A review. *Talanta*, 81(4–5), 1143–1152.
378 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2010.02.040>
- 379 Callejón, Raquel M., Amigo, J. M., Pairo, E., Garmón, S., Ocaña, J. A., & Morales, M. L. (2012).
380 Classification of Sherry vinegars by combining multidimensional fluorescence, parafac and
381 different classification approaches. *Talanta*, 88, 456–462.
382 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2011.11.014>
- 383 Carbonaro, C. M., Corpino, R., Chiriu, D., Ricci, P. C., Rivano, S., Salis, M., & Tuberoso, C. I. G.
384 (2019). Exploiting combined absorption and front face fluorescence spectroscopy to chase
385 classification: A proof of concept in the case of Sardinian red wines. *Spectrochimica Acta - Part*
386 *A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 214, 378–383.
387 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2019.02.041>
- 388 Chiappini, F. A., Alcaraz, M. R., Goicoechea, H. C., & Olivieri, A. C. (2019). A graphical user
389 interface as a new tool for scattering correction in fluorescence data. *Chemometrics and Intelligent*

390 *Laboratory Systems*, 193(June). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemolab.2019.07.009>

391 Fernstrom, J. D., & Fernstrom, M. H. (2007). Tyrosine, phenylalanine, and catecholamine synthesis
392 and function in the brain. *Journal of Nutrition*, 137(6), 1539–1547.
393 <https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/137.6.1539s>

394 Ferré, S., González-Ruiz, V., Guillarme, D., & Rudaz, S. (2019). Analytical strategies for the
395 determination of amino acids: Past, present and future trends. *Journal of Chromatography B:
396 Analytical Technologies in the Biomedical and Life Sciences*, 1132(September), 121819.
397 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2019.121819>

398 He, Y., Zhao, X. E., Wang, R., Wei, N., Sun, J., Dang, J., ... You, J. (2016). Simultaneous
399 Determination of Food-Related Biogenic Amines and Precursor Amino Acids Using in Situ
400 Derivatization Ultrasound-Assisted Dispersive Liquid-Liquid Microextraction by Ultra-High-
401 Performance Liquid Chromatography Tandem Mass Spectrometry. *Journal of Agricultural and
402 Food Chemistry*, 64(43), 8225–8234. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.6b03536>

403 Izquierdo Cañas, P. M., García Romero, E., Gómez Alonso, S., Fernández González, M., & Palop
404 Herreros, M. L. L. (2008). Amino acids and biogenic amines during spontaneous malolactic
405 fermentation in Tempranillo red wines. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 21(8), 731–
406 735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2007.11.002>

407 Jiménez Moreno, N., Torrea Goñ, D., & Ancín Azpilicueta, C. (2003). Changes in amine
408 concentrations during aging of red wine in oak barrels. *Journal of Agricultural and Food
409 Chemistry*, 51(19), 5732–5737. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf030254e>

410 Lorenzo, C., Bordiga, M., Pérez-Álvarez, E. P., Travaglia, F., Arlorio, M., Salinas, M. R., ... Garde-
411 Cerdán, T. (2017). The impacts of temperature, alcoholic degree and amino acids content on
412 biogenic amines and their precursor amino acids content in red wine. *Food Research
413 International*, 99(April), 328–335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2017.05.016>

414 Mandel, J., & Linnig, F. J. (1957). Study of Accuracy in Chemical Analysis Using Linear Calibration

415 Curves. *Analytical Chemistry*, 29(5), 743–749. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac60125a002>

416 Meléndez, M. E., Sarabia, L. A., & Ortiz, M. C. (2016). Distribution free methods to model the content
417 of biogenic amines in Spanish wines. *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems*, 155,
418 191–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemolab.2016.04.015>

419 Olivieri, A. C., Wu, H. L., & Yu, R. Q. (2009). MVC2: A MATLAB graphical interface toolbox for
420 second-order multivariate calibration. *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems*, 96(2),
421 246–251. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemolab.2009.02.005>

422 Önal, A., Tekkeli, S. E. K., & Önal, C. (2013). A review of the liquid chromatographic methods for the
423 determination of biogenic amines in foods. *Food Chemistry*, 138(1), 509–515.
424 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2012.10.056>

425 Ordóñez, J. L., Callejón, R. M., Troncoso, A. M., & García-Parrilla, M. C. (2017). Evaluation of
426 biogenic amines profile in opened wine bottles: Effect of storage conditions. *Journal of Food
427 Composition and Analysis*, 63(July), 139–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2017.07.042>

428 Palomino-Vasco, M., Acedo-Valenzuela, M. I., Rodríguez-Cáceres, M. I., & Mora-Diez, N. (2019).
429 Automated chromatographic method with fluorescent detection to determine biogenic amines and
430 amino acids. Application to craft beer brewing process. *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1601, 155–
431 163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2019.04.063>

432 Palomino-Vasco, M., Rodríguez-Cáceres, M. I., Mora-Diez, N., Pardo-Botello, R., & Acedo-
433 Valenzuela, M. I. (2019). Biogenic amines profile in red wines regarding aging and storage
434 conditions. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 83(July), 103295.
435 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2019.103295>

436 Papageorgiou, M., Lambropoulou, D., Morrison, C., Kłodzińska, E., Namieśnik, J., & Płotka-Wasyłka,
437 J. (2018). Literature update of analytical methods for biogenic amines determination in food and
438 beverages. *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 98, 128–142.
439 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2017.11.001>

440 Peña-Gallego, A., Hernández-Orte, P., Cacho, J., & Ferreira, V. (2012). High-Performance Liquid
441 Chromatography analysis of amines in must and wine: A review. *Food Reviews International*,
442 28(1), 71–96. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87559129.2011.594973>

443 Perestrelo, R., Bordiga, M., Locatelli, M., Silva, C., & Câmara, J. S. (2020). Polyphenols, biogenic
444 amines and amino acids patterns in Verdelho wines according to vintage. *Microchemical Journal*,
445 153(September 2019), 104383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2019.104383>

446 Petropoulos, S., Metafa, M., Kotseridis, Y., Paraskevopoulos, I., & Kallithraka, S. (2018). Amino acid
447 content of Agiorgitiko (*Vitis vinifera* L. cv.) grape cultivar grown in representative regions of
448 Nemea. *European Food Research and Technology*, 244(11), 2041–2050.
449 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-018-3115-3>

450 PubChem. (2020). L-tyrosine. Retrieved September 2, 2020, from
451 <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/L-tyrosine>

452 Ríos-Reina, R., Ocaña, J. A., Azcarate, S. M., Pérez-Bernal, J. L., Villar-Navarro, M., & Callejón, R.
453 M. (2019). Excitation-emission fluorescence as a tool to assess the presence of grape-must
454 caramel in PDO wine vinegars. *Food Chemistry*, 287(February), 115–125.
455 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2019.02.008>

456 Robles, A., Fabjanowicz, M., Chmiel, T., & Płotka-Wasyłka, J. (2019). Determination and
457 identification of organic acids in wine samples. Problems and challenges. *TrAC - Trends in*
458 *Analytical Chemistry*, 120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2019.115630>

459 Schenck, C. A., & Maeda, H. A. (2018). Tyrosine biosynthesis, metabolism, and catabolism in plants.
460 *Phytochemistry*, 149, 82–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2018.02.003>

461 Slominski, A., Zmijewski, M. A., & Pawelek, J. (2012). L-tyrosine and L-dihydroxyphenylalanine as
462 hormone-like regulators of melanocyte functions. *Pigment Cell and Melanoma Research*, 25(1),
463 14–27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-148X.2011.00898.x>

464 Valdés, M. E., Talaverano, M. I., Moreno, D., Prieto, M. H., Mancha, L. A., Uriarte, D., & Vilanova,

465 M. (2019). Effect of the timing of water deficit on the must amino acid profile of Tempranillo
466 grapes grown under the semiarid conditions of SW Spain. *Food Chemistry*, 292(October 2018),
467 24–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2019.04.046>
468

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Statistical analysis of the concentrations of biogenic amines and amino acids obtained by UHPLC-FD. Representation of the loadings graph (A) and the scores graph (B) obtained after Principal Component Analysis. The numbers identifying the samples correspond to the days on which the samples were collected. Class profile obtained by k-means method (C); and dendrogram (D) and class profile (E) obtained by Ward's method, obtained after Cluster Analysis.

Figure 2. PARAFAC components obtained, represented as three-dimensional spectra. Component 1 (C1) corresponds to TRP and component 3 (C3) corresponds to TYR. Component 2 (C2) corresponds to an unknown component of the wine samples.

Figure 3. Elliptical joint confidence regions (EJCR) test for TRP in test samples (red line), TYR in test samples (green line) and TYR in wine samples previously analysed by UHPLC-FLD (blue line). Ideal point (1, 0) represented by a black point.

Figure 4. Variation in TYR concentration (expressed in units of mg L^{-1}) over the days of the winemaking process (black points). In red, the polynomial function of grade 3 that approximately explains the concentration trend.

C1: Tryptophan

C2: Unknown component

C3: Tyrosine

Table 1. Analytes concentrations (standard deviation) chromatographically obtained for seven different days of winemaking sampling. LOD and LOQ stand for Limit of Detection (calculated by Long-Winfordner method) and Limit of Quantification (calculated as 3.3 times LOD), respectively, and are referred to those obtained in the validation of the UHPLC-FD method (Palomino-Vasco, Acedo-Valenzuela, Rodríguez-Cáceres, & Mora-Diez, 2019). All the concentrations are expressed in mg L⁻¹.

DAY	GLU	SER	HIS	ARG	GLY	TYR	LYS	PUT	AGM	CAD	ETA	TRP	HIM	PHE	TYM	TRY	PEA
0	0.6 (0.2)	0.20 (0.06)	0.6 (0.1)	2.9 (0.3)	0.08 (0.01)	3.3 (0.3)	<LOQ	0.05 (0.01)	0.08 (0.02)	0.16 (0.03)	0.14 (0.02)	0.6 (0.1)	<LOD	0.10 (0.04)	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
3	0.5 (0.1)	0.23 (0.08)	0.7 (0.1)	0.5 (0.1)	0.12 (0.01)	4.4 (0.4)	<LOQ	0.14 (0.03)	0.06 (0.02)	0.18 (0.03)	0.31 (0.04)	<LOQ	<LOD	0.15 (0.07)	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
10	0.8 (0.1)	0.32 (0.08)	0.9 (0.2)	0.9 (0.2)	0.17 (0.04)	5.5 (0.7)	<LOQ	0.19 (0.03)	0.13 (0.04)	0.34 (0.04)	0.39 (0.06)	1.4 (0.2)	<LOD	0.2 (0.1)	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
16	0.7 (0.1)	0.26 (0.08)	1.0 (0.2)	1.0 (0.2)	0.17 (0.02)	6.4 (0.8)	<LOQ	0.24 (0.04)	0.10 (0.05)	0.23 (0.04)	0.39 (0.06)	0.5 (0.1)	<LOD	0.2 (0.1)	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
21	0.5 (0.2)	0.4 (0.1)	0.8 (0.2)	0.9 (0.2)	0.22 (0.05)	6.7 (0.5)	<LOQ	0.22 (0.04)	0.10 (0.03)	0.16 (0.03)	0.48 (0.04)	<LOQ	<LOD	0.2 (0.1)	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
25	0.7 (0.3)	0.4 (0.1)	1.0 (0.2)	0.8 (0.2)	0.21 (0.03)	6.5 (0.8)	<LOQ	0.20 (0.02)	0.16 (0.03)	0.26 (0.03)	0.45 (0.04)	0.8 (0.1)	<LOD	0.2 (0.1)	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
28	0.6 (0.1)	0.34 (0.07)	0.8 (0.2)	0.8 (0.2)	0.19 (0.05)	7.2 (0.9)	<LOQ	0.20 (0.03)	0.15 (0.03)	0.25 (0.03)	0.40 (0.05)	0.51 (0.07)	<LOD	0.2 (0.1)	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
LOD	0.21	0.08	0.10	0.03	0.3	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.03	0.10	0.03	0.01	0.02
LOQ	0.68	0.26	0.32	0.09	0.10	0.18	0.07	0.03	0.10	0.05	0.02	0.41	0.08	0.35	0.09	0.03	0.08

Table 2. Nominal and predicted concentrations of TYR (SD) and TRP (SD), expressed in mg L⁻¹, as well as percentage of recovery, in test samples and in wine samples collected during the winemaking process.

	TYR			TRP		
Test sample	Nominal concentration	Predicted concentration	Recovery (%)	Nominal concentration	Predicted concentration	Recovery (%)
1	0.75	0.66 (0.02)	88.6	0.75	0.50 (0.05)	66.3
2	1.90	1.99 (0.03)	105.0	0.20	0.21 (0.07)	103.5
3	0.25	0.15 (0.03)	60.7	1.00	1.3 (0.1)	124.7
4	1.50	1.61 (0.03)	107.4	0.40	0.30 (0.06)	75.1
	MEAN RECOVERY (%)		90.4	MEAN RECOVERY (%)		92.4
Day of sampling	UHPLC-FLD concentration	Predicted concentration	Recovery (%)			
0	3.3 (0.3)	3.7 (0.3)	112.1			
3	4.4 (0.4)	6.5 (0.2)	147.7			
10	5.5 (0.7)	6.5 (0.2)	118.2			
16	6.4 (0.8)	6.8 (0.2)	106.3			
21	6.7 (0.5)	6.1 (0.2)	91.0			
25	6.5 (0.8)	6.8 (0.2)	104.6			
28	7.2 (0.9)	7.1 (0.2)	98.6			
	MEAN RECOVERY (%)		111.2			